

Exploring the Dimensions of Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction of Mixue Product

Slamet Heri Winarno^{1*}, Lela Elvira²

Universitas Bina Sarana Informatika

Corresponding Author: Slamet Heri Winarno slamet.smh@bsi.ac.id

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to explain the effect of applying the service dimension on customer satisfaction. Quality service is a comparison between the service felt by customers and the quality of service that customers expect through its dimensions. Research is descriptive and quantitative, looking for causality between the variables studied. This research focused on 100 sample people who were customers of Mixue start-up products located in Depok, West Java, and surrounding areas. Data collection used questionnaires and was obtained using the SEM method of path analysis. The results showed that of the five dimensions of service, one, namely responsiveness, did not have a significant influence on customer satisfaction. The validity test results show that all question items are valid, and the research model is feasible or reliable to use. This study also resulted in a squared multiple correlation (R^2) value of 0.604, where customer satisfaction can be explained by service dimensions of 60.4%.

INTRODUCTION

Each type of business (company) has the same main goal in its business, which is to achieve profitability (Pakurár et al., 2019) and satisfy its customers (Winarno et al., 2020). Customer satisfaction (Afthanorhan et al., 2019) will certainly provide many benefits for the company, such as generating customer trust that can encourage the creation of customer loyalty (Yeong et al., 2022), providing a good image for the company (Winarno et al., 2018), and of course increasing the company's profit. A measurable strategy is needed to be successful in the business world and also in facing competition, one of which is by trying to create and provide satisfactory services (Haryeni & Yendra, 2019). Satisfaction is a very decisive factor in marketing (Lubis & Andayani, 2018); on the contrary, if customers feel disappointed in service, it will be a ruin for the company itself (Nanincova, 2019).

Quality of service is reflected in dimensions such as responsiveness, attention, physical evidence, assurance, and reliability (Brajčić et al., 2021). If done well, it will create satisfaction for its customers (Gea & Mendrofa, 2022). This is a form of comparison between the service felt by customers and the quality of service expected by customers (Indra & Siagian, 2021). If the perceived service dimensions equal or exceed the expected service quality, then the service is said to be of high quality and satisfactory (Giao & Trang, 2019). The goal of this research is to examine how service dimensions can create or deplete customer satisfaction.

The object of research was chosen for research purposes, namely the culinary model of ice cream, Mixue, which is currently developing and becoming viral on various social media platforms. The high level of interest from customers who visit each Mixue outlet is something unique and important to research because this relatively new product has turned out to be in great demand by various levels of society. This is what makes this research focus on analyzing the influence of the service dimension on the creation of customer satisfaction.

(Tešić, 2020) says quality of service is a handling that is expected to meet the needs of those customers. Service quality is also a way to meet the needs and desires of consumers, and the accuracy of their delivery helps meet those expectations (Winarno et al., 2020). A measure of service quality is the level of superiority that is expected to meet customer needs (Afthanorhan et al., 2019). Furthermore, Nurjanah et al. (2021) said that service quality is a comparison between the service felt and the expected service. Service quality can also be interpreted as the best service provided to customers for satisfaction, accompanied by professional efforts to prepare services (Putra et al., 2021).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Principles in service quality (Pakurár et al., 2019) include: (1) making it easier for customers to contact people who can solve problems quickly; (2) knowing that the problem will be resolved as soon as possible; (3) expecting the presence of customers as soon as possible; and (4) responding as quickly as possible and trying to explain what happened and when. (Tešić, 2020) said there are five dimensions of service quality, namely: (1) reliability, the

company's ability to respond quickly, accurately, and in a timely manner to customer requests related to services that can satisfy customers; (2) responsiveness, initiatives that arise from employees to provide fast and responsive service to customers; (3) assurance, the attitude or characteristics of employees that can instill trust in customers that include a polite, knowledgeable, competent, and credible attitude to make customers feel comfortable with the services provided by the company; (4) attention (empathy), a form of attention given by the company to customers in the form of understanding customer needs and attention to provide convenience in communicating with the company; (5) tangible evidence (competent employees, procurement of complete facilities, and modern and sophisticated telecommunications equipment).

Meanwhile, Broto (2020) and Rasyid (2017) stated that there are three characteristics of service quality, namely: (1) intangible because service quality is not a product; (2) heterogeneous and variegated because the outcome depends on the actions carried out by the individuals involved, from producers to consumers who may not have the same expectations; and (3) the indivisible or inseparability of the production and consumption processes, which occur synchronously. The most important feature of the inseparability of the service is that the company must strive to ensure that when the service is being produced, the manufacturer must know the maximum number of consumers who will use the service.

(Winarno et al., 2020) mentioned that customer satisfaction is how well the perceived performance of a product matches buyer expectations. Customer satisfaction, according to Nalendra et al. (2021), is a response to the fulfillment of consumer needs. On the other hand, Nanincova (2019) stated that customer satisfaction is an important key to customer loyalty, so without customer satisfaction, the company will find it difficult to survive in the face of competition (Yuniasih et al., 2022). Similar to Kotler & Keller (2007), customer satisfaction is the level of a person's feelings after comparing perceived performance or results with their expectations (Pane et al., 2018).

There are three dimensions of customer satisfaction (Indra & Siagian, 2021), namely: (1) expectation, (2) performance, and (3) experience. Meanwhile, (Paul & Pradhan, 2019) stated that there are five main factors that need to be considered in customer satisfaction, including: (1) product quality; consumers will be satisfied if the evaluation results show that the product they use is of high quality, the product is said to be quality for someone if the product can affect; (2) service quality; consumers will be satisfied if they receive good service and meet their expectations; (3) emotional; consumers will be satisfied if they receive good service and meet their expectations.

Service quality is basically the optimal service provided by professional company officers to customers for their satisfaction, accompanied by professional efforts to prepare services that satisfy customers (Pakurár et al., 2019). If the quality of the company's service is linked to retaining consumers, then the influence can be known from consumer behavior; behavioral intentions can be seen as an indicator that indicates whether the customer will stay or

leave the company (Yeong et al., 2022). Furthermore, Afthanorhan et al. (2019) revealed that good-quality service will certainly have a big influence on the satisfaction felt by customers.

Research Model

Based on this explanation, a research model was formed, as shown in figure 1

Figure 1. Research Model

A hypothesis is a temporary conjecture about the formulation of a research problem; therefore, the formulation of a research problem is usually arranged in the form of a statement sentence. The hypotheses in this study are:

H1: It is suspected that there is a significant influence between reliability and customer satisfaction.

H2: It is suspected that there is a significant influence between responsiveness and customer satisfaction.

H3: It is suspected that there is a significant effect of assurance on customer satisfaction.

H4: It is suspected that there is a significant influence between emphaty and customer satisfaction.

H5: It is suspected that there is a significant influence between tangible and customer satisfaction.

METHODOLOGY

This research is descriptive and quantitative, determining the relationship or influence between the variables used. The variable in question is service, which is reflected in the dimensions of service (X) and customer satisfaction (Y) for customers of Mixue's new product, which is one of the start-ups that focuses on culinary business in the form of ice cream sales.

Sampling is done using the simple random sampling technique, which is a sampling technique where researchers take samples by giving equal opportunities to all members of the population to be designated as members of the sample. With this sampling technique, 100 respondents were obtained who became customers of Mixue ice cream products spread across several areas in the city of Depok, West Java. The data collection method uses: (1) observation methods, by observing the behavior of the customers studied; and (2)

questionnaire methods, by distributing questionnaires to parties or people who are used as respondents. The data were analyzed using structural equation modeling (SEM) path analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This research is aimed at respondents who have a history of purchasing new products in the form of ice cream at Mixue. The characteristics of the respondents obtained include gender, age, occupation, and income (Table 1).

Table 1. Characteristics of Respondents

	Characteristic	Sum	Percentage	
	Gender:			
	Man	40	40%	
	Woman	60	60%	
	Age:			
	< 20 Years	11	11%	
	20 - 30 Years	79	79%	
	31 - 40 Years	3	3%	
	41 - 50 Years	5	5%	
	> 50 Years	2	2%	
The	Work:			validity test used as a measure of whether or a
is	Students	38	38%	
	Private	14	14%	
not	Entrepreneurial	2	2%	
	Government employees	4	4%	
	Other	42	42%	
	Income:			
All	< Rp. 1 million	25	25%	equations must also be numbered
	Rp. 1 Million - 3 Million	37	37%	
	Rp. 3 Million - 5 Million	32	32%	
	> Rp. 5 Million	6	6%	

Source: Data Processed (2022)

Questionnaire is valid. Instruments that are said to be valid when showing the measuring instrument used to obtain data are valid or can be used to measure what should be measured (Nanincova, 2019). The minimum requirement to qualify for validity is a r_count greater than or equal to 0.3, or by comparing the rcount value with a rtable. If the value of r_count is greater than r_table, then it can be said to be valid, and vice versa.

The number of respondents in the study was recorded as 100, so the r_table value could be obtained using the r-product moment person table with the formula df (degree of freedom) = n-2, so that df = 100 - 2 = 98 with an error rate of 5% would result in a r_table of 0.197. The calculation results in tables 2 show the r_count value > r_table, so it can be said that all question items used are valid.

Table 2. Validity Test Results

	Indicator	r_count	r_table	Result
<i>Reliability</i>	X1	0,635	0,197	Valid
	X2	0,679	0,197	Valid
	X3	0,727	0,197	Valid
<i>Responsiveness</i>	X4	0,739	0,197	Valid
	X5	0,769	0,197	Valid
	X6	0,686	0,197	Valid
	X7	0,789	0,197	Valid
<i>Assurance</i>	X8	0,787	0,197	Valid
	X9	0,764	0,197	Valid
	X10	0,762	0,197	Valid
	X11	0,643	0,197	Valid
<i>Emphaty</i>	X12	0,760	0,197	Valid
	X13	0,725	0,197	Valid
	X14	0,808	0,197	Valid
<i>Tangible</i>	X15	0,725	0,197	Valid
	X16	0,649	0,197	Valid
	X17	0,754	0,197	Valid
<i>Customer Satisfaction</i>	Y1	0,635	0,197	Valid
	Y2	0,679	0,197	Valid
	Y3	0,727	0,197	Valid

Source: Data Processed (2022)

A reliability test is a test used to determine whether an instrument is reliable or not. A reliability test is a tool for determining the dependability of a questionnaire that serves as an indicator of a variable or construct. To find out whether a variable is reliable or not, a statistical test is carried out by looking at the value of cronbach's alpha with the following criteria:

1. If the cronbach's alpha value is greater than 0.60, the variables being measured are reliable.
2. If the value of cronbach alpha is less than 0.60, then the questions used to measure the variable are not reliable.

Tables 4 and 5 show the results of the reliability test for the dimensions of service and customer satisfaction. To determine whether the instrument is reliable or not, a Cronbach's alpha boundary is used on a scale of 0.61-0.80. If less than 0.6 is declared sufficiently reliable, while above 0.7 is declared reliable or acceptable, and if above 0.8 is declared very reliable.

Table 3. Reliability Test Results

Measure	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Dimensions of Service	.845	17
Customer Satisfaction	.798	3

Source: Data Processed (2022)

The results of calculating the value of cronbach's alpha for the service dimension show a number of 0.845 and can be concluded to be very reliable, while the value of Cronbach's alpha for customer satisfaction is 0.798, which means reliable. Before conducting the signification test, data processing was carried out which had been successfully collected through questionnaires and respondents' answers had been obtained. After tabulation of the data instruments, data processing is then carried out using the SEM method and produces outputs as presented in Figure 2, as a follow-up to the calculations of the research model.

Figure 2. Research Model Calculation Results
 Source: Data Processed (2022)

Other outputs provide the mean and intercept values of the model with an intercept value of 1,505, as well as the correlation coefficients of each service dimension (table 4).

Table 4. Correlation & Determination Result

			Estimate
Satisfaction	<---	Responsiveness	-0,021
Satisfaction	<---	Emphaty	0,198
Satisfaction	<---	Tangible	0,189
Satisfaction	<---	Assurance	0,240
Satisfaction	<---	Reliability	0,185
Intercept			1,505
Coefficient of Determination			0,604

Source: Data Processed (2022)

The values in tables 5 can also form a regression equation, namely:

$$\text{Satisfaction} = 1,505 - 0,021\text{responsiveness} + 0,198\text{emphaty} + 0,189\text{tangible} + 0,240\text{assurance} + 0,185\text{reliability}$$

The value of the coefficient of determination is shown by the squared multiple correlation (R²) value in table 10, which is 0.604, which means that the satisfaction variable that can be explained by the dimensions of the service variable in the form of assurance, reliability, physical evidence, attention, and responsiveness is 60.4%, while 39.6% is another variable that was not studied. It can be concluded that the model is quite good.

Regression weight gives the magnitude of the value of the unstandardized and standardized regression coefficients. Unstandardized value + standard error (SE) = standardized value. The critical value (CR) is equal to the value of t in the OLS regression, and P is the degree of significance

Table 4. Signification Results

	Estimate	P	Information
Satisfaction <--- Responsiveness	-,027	,827	Rejected
Satisfaction <--- Emphaty	,209	***	Accepted
Satisfaction <--- Tangible	,182	***	Accepted
Satisfaction <--- Assurance	,317	***	Accepted
Satisfaction <--- Reliability	,171	***	Accepted

Source: Data Processed (2022)

probability, with *** meaning that it is by default significant at 0.001 (table 4). This illustrates that responsiveness has no effect on customer satisfaction because the probability value is far above 0,005, emphaty has a positive and significant effect on satisfaction with a standardized coefficient of 0,209 (an increase of 1 unit of emphaty will increase satisfaction by 0,209), tangible has a positive and significant effect on satisfaction with a standardized coefficient of 0,182 (an increase of 1 unit of tangible will increase satisfaction by 0,182), assurance has a positive and significant effect on satisfaction with a standardized coefficient of 0,317 (an increase of 1 unit of assurance will increase satisfaction by 0,317), reliability has a positive and significant effect on satisfaction with a standardized coefficient of 0,171 (an increase of 1 unit of reliability will increase satisfaction by 0,171).

Reliability Positively and Significantly Affects Customer Satisfaction (H1).

The test results on the service dimension in the form of reliability show a significant influence on customer satisfaction. This reflects that respondents gave a good assessment to Mixue, who has been able to provide accurate affirmations about the products offered. In addition, Mixue is also able to overcome every complaint and customer complaint related to the product quickly and still prioritize optimal service. Respondents also assessed that Mixue's employees had good knowledge of the products offered (product knowledge).

Responsiveness has no Positive or non Significant Effect on Customer Satisfaction (H2).

The results of other respondents' assessments that responsiveness does not affect customer satisfaction are based on responses from customers who state that some of the employees have not been able to work quickly in taking action and solving problems.

Assurance Positively and Significantly Affects Customer Satisfaction (H3).

On the other hand, the behavior and attitude of employees in providing services are considered to have met customer expectations, so respondents rated Mixue employees as people who are suitable to work in their fields.

Empathy has a Positive and Significant Effect on Customer Satisfaction (H4).

The ability to communicate well, be able to understand and fulfill customer wishes, and provide services are the main factors that make the dimension of attention affect customer satisfaction. Respondents judged that what each Mixue employee had done had succeeded in making them satisfied and happy.

Tangible Positively and Significantly Affects Customer Satisfaction (H5).

Mixue is a business that is currently going viral, where the products presented are in great demand by customers, with a varied business concept and strong branding making Mixue products able to compete with similar products. Besides that, it is also supported by the appearance of trendy employees, the completeness of supporting goods, and digital transaction facilities so that Mixue can develop. Customer satisfaction can be positively impacted by high-quality services. Studies by (Paraskevas and Papathanasiou, 2011) demonstrate that customer satisfaction is significantly influenced by the quality of the services provided. Customer satisfaction levels can be impacted by how simple it is to acquire services. According to research by (Bitner and Hubbert, 2005), accessibility to services is a factor that influences consumer satisfaction across a range of businesses.

Customer satisfaction levels can be influenced by sound service presumptions and capabilities. Customer satisfaction in the service sector is significantly impacted by service answers and capabilities, according to studies done by (Paraskevas and Papathanasiou, 2011). Customer satisfaction levels can be impacted through empathetic service. (Hwang and Lee's, 2010) research demonstrates that customer happiness is significantly impacted by the use of empathy in service.

CONCLUSIONS

The results of the study can be concluded that service dimensions play an important role in determining the level of customer satisfaction. The dimensions of service quality, assurance, reliability, tangible, empathy, and responsiveness all have a significant influence on customer satisfaction. Result of squared multiple correlation or coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.604,

which can be interpreted to mean that the dimensions of service variables have an influence of 60.4% on customer satisfaction and the rest are influenced by other factors that are not included in this research variable; Mixue's service quality, which is reflected in the service dimension, is considered to have been able to create customer satisfaction for the products offered.

Therefore, Mixue must pay attention to each service dimension in providing quality services and meeting customer expectations. Providing quality service can help companies retain existing customers and acquire new customers. This conclusion suggests that companies should pay attention to overall service quality, including factors such as service quality, ease of access, service responsiveness and capability, and empathy, to increase customer satisfaction levels. The efforts or strategies that need to be carried out by Mixue from the employee aspect are to increase the responsiveness of each employee, so Mixue needs to provide training again to be able to work quickly in serving, taking action, and solving problems.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations so that further research is still needed on this topic "Exploring the Dimensions of Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction of Mixue Product."

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